

ANALYSIS OF CLIMATE SUITABILITY FOR GRAPES PLANTATION AND ITS PROJECTION IN BALI PROVINCE

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Abstract

The government begins to increase the development of agriculture, one of which is the cultivation of grapes. A study indicated that Buleleng Regency in Bali Province was one of wine centers in Indonesia. Regarding to that, it is important to know the land suitability for grape plantation to generate the best product of grapes either can be used as a recommendation for investment of wine development. The data used consisted of monthly rainfall and air temperature period of 1981-2015, soil textures and slopes. The projection data generated from scenario model of Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP4.5) for air temperature and rainfall extracted from GCM MIROC5 (Model for Interdisciplinary Research on Climate). The climatic suitability for grape crops weighted by the score of rainfall, air temperature, number of dry months, soil texture, altitudes, and slopes. The results indicate that suitable area (S) in Bali for first projected period (2021-2030) decreased up to 16% compared to the baseline period (2006-2015). The area with unsuitable (N) and suitable (S) classification reaches 330,332 ha (58.6%) and 233,090ha (41.4%) respectively. The projection for next 20 years (2031-2040) resulted similar pattern where most of the decrease of suitable area occur in unsuitable place for plantation development.

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1. Introduction

Bali is one of the tourist destinations that has a variety of cultures and an abundance of natural resources. The area of Bali Province reaches 5,636.66 km² or 0.29 % of the area of Indonesia [1]. Natural wealth is the main sources in improving human living standards [2]. Besides continuing to develop the tourism, Bali also begins to improve the development of agriculture, one of which is the cultivation of grape. In the field of agriculture, finding the optimal location for plantation can improve the harvest success and reduce the adverse effects that caused by the environment. A plant will shortly become unproductive if it is forced to grow in the inappropriate location unless improvements are made such as with technology inputs [3]. This shows how the area's incompatibility in developing particular plant commodities is closely related to the climate and soil conditions [4]. Some regions that produce grapes in Indonesia are East Java (Probolinggo, Pasuruan, Situbondo), Bali, and Kupang [5]. According to Regional Regulation No. 4 of 1996, Bali Province at the direction of developing West Bali as a center of horticulture, especially fruits, Buleleng Regency is very suitable for the cultivation of grapes [6], supported by a study from the Agricultural Research and Development Agency (Balitbangtan) in 2012 concerning to land area and potential for grapes development in Indonesia resulted Buleleng Regency in Bali Province is one of the centers of grapes in Indonesia with 900 to 1000 ha (hectares) area where about 800 ha has been managed.

The projection of climate condition in the future can be identified by using climate scenarios, one of which is Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP). RCP scenario is a renewal from the previous scenario called Special Reports on Emission Scenario (SRES) which is based on research with four

climate modeling equated with carbon gas concentrations namely RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP6.0, and RCP8.5. The use of scenario is not aimed at predicting the future but to understand more about the uncertainties and alternatives of the future better [7]. This study described climate projection using the RCP4.5 scenario with MIROC5 (Model for Interdisciplinary Research on Climate) model with a resolution of 20 km. RCP4.5 is a stability scenario where total radiative forcing is stabilized quickly after 2100 without exceeding the long-term radiative forcing target level [8]. The advantage of the RCP4.5 scenario is that it represents a current situation where there is a policy to limit greenhouse gas emissions through the Kyoto Protocol. The model contains climate data that simulate the present (period of 2006-2015) as baseline information and future climate projection for the near (period of 2021-2030 and 2031-2040) which are then used as input to calculate the climate suitability weight at the projection period for grapes. The results of the climate projection give an overview of the climate condition until 2040 which are used in this research as an illustration of the future condition. It can provide information for development planning policy in the area which grape plantation are suitable with in order to produce grapes maximally in the future.

2. Data and Method

The data used consisted of monthly rainfall period of 1981-2015 observed at 60 stations that represent each district over Bali and monthly air temperature period of 1981-2015 observed at three reference stations. These three reference stations are Jembrana Climatological Station, Ngurah Rai Meteorological Station, and Kahang-Kahang Geophysical Station. Estimation of monthly average air temperature carried out by Braak formula (1928) [9], where the temperature increased with altitude expressed by this following formula:

$$Th = Th_0 - (0.6 \times h \times 0.01) \quad (1)$$

Where Th is the air temperature in the rain post ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), Th_0 is the air temperature at the reference station ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), h is the height difference between the station and the reference stations (m). Meanwhile, the model uses MIROC5 data from RCP4.5 scenario which contains rainfall and air temperature data. RCP 4.5 data is a stability scenario where total radiative forcing is stabilized quickly after 2100 without exceeding the long-term radiative forcing target level [8]. This model data is then divided into four periods, the present (period of 2006-2015) and near (period of 2021-2030 and 2031-2040). Furthermore, monthly rainfall is corrected by the following formula [10]:

$$CH_{model_kor} = CH_{mod} \times \frac{\overline{CH}_{obs}}{\overline{CH}_{mod}} \quad (2)$$

Where CH_{model_kor} is corrected rainfall generated by model, CH_{mod} is monthly rainfall generated by model before correction, \overline{CH}_{obs} is the average of observed monthly rainfall of the baseline, and \overline{CH}_{mod} is the average of modelled monthly rainfall of the baseline. Meanwhile the air temperature is corrected using the following formula [10]:

$$T_{Model_cor} = T_{Mod} + (\overline{T}_{Obs} - \overline{T}_{Mod}) \quad (3)$$

Where T_{Model_cor} is corrected temperature generated by model T_{Mod} is monthly temperature generated by model before correction, \overline{T}_{obs} is the average of observed monthly temperature of the baseline, and \overline{T}_{mod} is the average of modelled monthly temperature of the baseline.

According to Food and Agricultural Organization (1976) in the framework for land evaluation defined that land suitability is the level of suitability of a field for a particular crop use [11]. Thus, climate suitability is the level of suitability of climate elements for a plant life in a field of land. The land suitability classification system in this study used land suitability ordo which showed the level of land suitability described as follows:

a. Suitable (S)

The land does not have significant limiting factors for sustainable uses, or limiting factors are minor and will not affect land productivity significantly.

b. Not Suitable (N)

The land has the very heavy level of limitation and difficult to overcome or cannot be repaired with the current level of knowledge with rational cost.

Weighting is a decision-making technique in a process that involves various factors together by giving the weight to each factor [12]. The weighting can be made objectively with statistical calculations or subjectively by setting particular considerations [13]. In this study, the weighting was carried out using 6 variables which consist of rainfall, air temperature, number of dry months that is based on Schmidt and Ferguson criteria, soil texture, slope, and altitude that is based on the weighting of climate suitability for grapes. The weighting value in the determination of the climate suitability of grapes described in Table 1.

TABLE 1. The Weighting of Climate Suitability for Grapes.

Ket.	The use requirement/Land characteristic classes	Weight		
		4	3	2
B1	Average of monthly air temperature (°C)	22 – 28	28 – 32 18 – 22	< 18 , > 32
B2	Annually rainfall (mm)	1.000 - 2.000	800 - 1.000 2.000 - 3.500	< 800 , > 3.500
B3	Length of dry month)	3 – 4	4 – 6	< 3 , > 6
B4	Soil texture	fine, slightly coarse	-	-
B5	Slope (%)/erosion hazard	< 8 ; Very low erosion	8 - 16 ; Low-medium erosion	> 16 ; Heavy erosion
B6	altitude (m)	0 – 300 0 – 800	800 - 1.000	> 1.000

The scores of each element then are summed to get the climate suitability level of the grapes. Here is a formula to get the total score:

$$Total\ Score = (B1 + B2 + B3 + B4 + B5 + B6) \quad (4)$$

The total scores determine the classification of climate suitability of grapes which consist of S (suitable) and N (not suitable). The level of climate suitability of grapes plantation are based on the total of weights as shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2. THE WEIGHT TOTAL CLASSIFICATION OF CLIMATE SUITABILITY FOR GRAPES

Suitability Classification	Weight Total
suitable (S)	19 – 24
Not Suitable (N)	10 – 18

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Distribution of Climate Suitability for Grapes Plantation Based on Observed Baseline Period and Distribution of Climate Suitability for Grapes Plantation Based on Modeled Baseline Period

The climate suitability of grapes in this study was analyzed by using six variables consisting of three dynamic parameters and three static parameters. Dynamic parameters consist of rainfall, dry months, and air temperature. static parameters consist of soil texture, altitude, and slope which in this study are considered not to change until 2040. The following picture shows the distribution of climate suitability for grapes during the observed baseline period.

FIGURE 1. MAP OF CLIMATE SUITABILITY FOR GRAPES DURING OBSERVED BASELINE PERIOD (1981-2010) OVER BALI PROVINCE

FIGURE 2. MAP OF CLIMATE SUITABILITY FOR GRAPES AT MODELED BASELINE PERIOD (2006-2015) OVER BALI PROVINCE

TABLE 3. AREA PERCENTAGE OF CLIMATE SUITABILITY FOR GRAPES IN BALI PROVINCE AT OBSERVED BASELINE PERIOD (1981- 2010)

No.	Regency	Regency Area (ha)	S		N			
			Area (ha)	(%)	Region	Area (ha)	(%)	Region
1	Badung	41852	26458	63.2	most area	15344	36.7	north, east
2	Bangli	52081	6493	12.5	north	45596	87.5	most area

3	Buleleng	136588	89544	65.6	most area	46892	34.3	southeast, centre, north
4	Denpasar	12778	9473	74.1	most area	3307	25.9	northeast
5	Gianyar	36800	4815	13.1	north	31974	86.9	most area
6	Jembrana	84180	84180	100.0	all region	-	-	
7	Karangasem	83954	-	-		83954	100.0	all region
8	Klungkung	31500	-	-		31500	100.0	all region
9	Tabanan	83933	57896	69.0	most area	26023	31.0	northeast
Total		563666	278860	49.5		284590	50.5	

Table 3 shows that the most extensive of the suitable area is Buleleng regency with 89,544 ha or 65.6% of the total area of Buleleng regency where Buleleng regency is an existing grapes center in Bali province followed by Jembrana regency with 84,180 ha or 100% of the total area of Jembrana regency. The most extensive of the not suitable area is Karangasem regency with 83,954 ha or 100% of the total area of Karangasem regency, and Klungkung regency with 31,500 ha or 100% of the total area of Klungkung regency.

TABEL 4. AREA PERCENTAGE OF CLIMATE SUITABILITY FOR GRAPES IN BALI PROVINCE AT MODELED BASELINE PERIOD (2006-2016)

NO	Regency	Regency Area (ha)	S			N		
			Area (ha)	(%)	Region	Area (ha)	(%)	Region
1	Badung	41.852	24.229	57.9	most area	17.573	42.0	north, east
2	Bangli	52.081	6.492	12.5	North	45.595	87.5	most area
3	Buleleng	136.588	98.505	72.1	most area	37.933	27.8	southeast, central
4	Denpasar	12.778	2.755	21.6	South	10.034	78.5	most area
5	Gianyar	36.800	4.815	13.1	north	31.974	86.9	most area
6	Jembrana	84.180	84.180	100.0	all regions	-	-	
7	Karangasem	83.954	-	-		83.954	100.0	all regions
8	Klungkung	31.500	-	-		31.500	100.0	all regions
9	Tabanan	83.933	57.896	69.0	most area	26.023	31.0	East
Total		563.666	278.871	49.5		284.586	50.5	

3.3 Distribution of Climate Suitability for Grapes Plantation Based on First Projected Period (2021-2030) and Distribution of Climate Suitability for Grapes Plantation Based on Second Projected Period (2031-2040)

Figure 3. shows the climate suitability at projected period (period of 2021-2030) where half of Bali Province are categorized as suitable area and Figure 4 shows the climate suitability for grape plantation at projected period (2031-2040) where more than half area of Bali categorized as not suitable area.

FIGURE 3. MAP OF CLIMATE SUITABILITY FOR GRAPES PLANTATION AT FIRST PROJECTED PERIOD (2021-2030) OVER BALI PROVINCE

FIGURE 4. MAP OF CLIMATE SUITABILITY FOR GRAPES PLANTATION AT SECOND PROJECTED PERIOD (2031-2040) OVER BALI

TABLE 5. AREA PERCENTAGE OF CLIMATE SUITABILITY FOR GRAPES PLANTATION IN BALI PROVINCE AT PROJECTED PERIOD (2021-2030)

NO	Regency	Regency Area (ha)	S			N		
			Area (ha)	(%)	Region	Area (ha)	(%)	Region
1	Badung	41.852	22.508	53.8	most area	19.296	46.1	north, central, east
2	Bangli	52.081	6.490	12.5	North	45.596	87.5	most area
3	Buleleng	136.588	89.292	65.4	most area	47.144	34.5	southeast, east
4	Denpasar	12.778	2.754	21.6	South	10.034	78.5	most area
5	Gianyar	36.800	-	-		36.800	100.0	all regions
6	Jembrana	84.180	74.012	87.9	most area	10.150	12.1	Southeast
7	Karangasem	83.954	6.423	7.7	North	77.503	92.3	most area
8	Klungkung	31.500	-	-		31.500	100.0	all regions

9	Tabanan	83.933	31.611	37.7	South	52.310	62.3	most area
Total		563.666	233.090	41.4		330.332	58.6	

TABLE 6. AREA PERCENTAGE OF CLIMATE SUITABILITY FOR GRAPES IN BALI PROVINCE AT PROJECTED PERIOD (2031-2040)

No	Regency	Regency Area (Ha)	S			N		
			Area (ha)	(%)	Region	Area (ha)	(%)	Region
1	Badung	41852	22508	53.8	most area	19296	46.1	north, central, east
2	Bangli	52081	6490	12.5	North	45596	87.5	most area
3	Buleleng	136588	89292	65.4	most area	47144	34.5	southeast, south
4	Denpasar	12778	2754	21.6	South	10034	78.5	most area
5	Gianyar	36800	-	-		36800	100.0	all region
6	Jembrana	84180	74012	87.9	most area	10150	12.1	Southeast
7	Karangasem	83954	6423	7.7	North	77503	92.3	most area
8	Klungkung	31500	-	-		31500	100.0	all regions
9	Tabanan	83933	31611	37.7	South	52310	62.3	most area
Total		563666	233090	41.4		330332	58.6	

3.5 Map of Land Use

According to Turner et al. (1995), land use defined as a condition which consists of two main things, which are how biophysical characteristics of the land are changed or manipulated and the purpose of the engineering [14]. Meyer (1995) also mentioned that land use is the way how humans utilize land and resources to obtain the purpose of the land use [14]. Land use maps below are recommendations that might be possible for plantation development in the Province of Bali so it may give general information about the suitable area for plantation development.

FIGURE 5. MAP OF LAND USE FOR PLANTATION DEVELOPMENT

Based on Figure 5, most areas in Bali Province might be able for plantation development. The classification which is considered possible consist of grass or vacant land, moor or fields, gardens, forests, and shrubs. These five criteria are considered possible to meet the criteria for plantation development.

3.5 Discussion

The distribution of climate suitability for grapes at existing period (observed baseline period of 1981-2010) in each regency in Bali Province show that half of the areas are classified into suitable category because the growth of the grapes requirements have been properly fulfilled such as the annual rainfall ranges 1.000-2.000 mm, the average temperature is about 25 ° C, the average number of dry months in the west to the south Bali province in a year ranges 3-4 months and the average of altitude is about 345 m, and the slope is around 8-16%. Meanwhile, half of the other areas of Bali Province, which those are in the northeast to the southeastern part of Bali Province are classified into not suitable category including entire Nusa Penida Island as well. It caused by the average altitude in the regions range more than 1000 m, the annual average rainfall ranges more than 2.000 mm and the soil textures are slightly fine which are not suitable for growing grapes. Therefore, these parameter scores and weights are less to fit into the suitable category which means that the area is less supportive for the growth of grapes.

The region of grapes centers that already exist in Bali like Buleleng Regency, is also dominated by a suitable category because the environmental requirement of grapes growth based on climate parameters have been fulfilled. The half of the suitable areas for grape plantation are also mostly matched with the land use map (Figure 5). Almost the entire suitable areas allow the plantation development because the areas are dominated by grass or vacant land, moor or fields, gardens, forests, and shrubs. There are several areas that classified to the suitable category but the land use is not recommended for plantation development like in the south to east Tabanan Regency and almost the entire Denpasar and Badung Regency.

This also happens and applies to climate suitability at the modeled baseline period (period of 2006-2015) which show half of the area in Bali Province are classified to suitable area spreading from

the west to the south and the north evenly. The results of climate suitability for grapes show a similar percentage between observed baseline period and RCP 4.5 Modeled baseline period which has 49.5 % suitable and 50.5% not suitable. However, there are several regencies that experience an increase and decrease in percentage area such as the Buleleng Regency where the suitable percentage increased. Badung Regency and Denpasar experience a decrease for the suitable area and vice versa. This is because in the modeled baseline period of average annual rainfall increases and the dry month decreases thus affecting the weight value for climate suitability.

Furthermore, according to modeled projection data (period of 2021-2030), the climate suitability for grapes will become even not suitable compared to the baseline period as seen as more than half area of Bali Province are classified into the not suitable (N). the not suitable land area is 330.332 ha (58.6%) and the suitable land area (S) is 233.090 ha (41.4%). This caused by the scenario projected an increase in annual rainfall which is less ideal for grapes. There are five regencies that experienced a decreased in the percentage of area, which are Badung, Buleleng, Gianyar, Jembrana, and Tabanan regency. It is because the rainfall and temperature have increased by almost 2° C compared to the baseline period and the number of dry months has decreased which later affect the climate suitability for grapes. More than half of the not suitable areas for grape plantation are also mostly matched with the land use map (Figure 5). Almost the entire of not suitable areas do not allow the plantation development because the areas are not dominated by grass or vacant land, moor or fields, gardens, forests, and shrubs. There are several areas that classified to not the suitable category but the land use is recommended for plantation development like the most area of Nusa Penida Island, Klungkung, and southern Buleleng Regency.

The projection for the period of 2031-2040 did not show a different pattern. According to Table 5, Table 6, Figure 3 and Figure 4, the projected climate suitability for grapes at the period of 2021-20130 and period of 2031-20140 resulted in similar percentage where 41.4% of the area is categorized suitable and 58.6% are categorized not suitable. It means that there is no climate suitability change within the two projection periods.

4. Conclusion

According to the results and analysis of projection data for the period of 2021-2030 and 2031-2040, climate suitability for grapes with suitable (S) condition decreases compared to the baseline period. This caused by the projection data resulted an increase in annual rainfall and monthly temperature that makes grapes plantation less ideal.

5. References

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